

Mapping of maDMPs to Funder Templates

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With funding agencies and other organisations now requiring that DMPs be submitted together with funding proposals, there has been an increase in the number of distinct DMP templates. The DCS application profile should cover the knowledge required by some of the most popular templates.

Objectives

The objective of this hackathon team was to go through the process of mapping the DCS application profile to several of the most commonly used DMP templates. To that effect each question of a DMP Template was analysed for one or multiple matching fields in the DCS application profile. The following DMP templates were considered: (1) [H2020 DMP Template](#); (2) [Science Europe Core Requirements for Data Management Plans](#); (3) [National Science Foundation \(NSF\) GENERIC Core Requirements for DMPs Questions](#); and (4) [U.S. Geological Survey \(USGS\)](#).

Methodology

There were three rules that were put in place at the onset of the hackathon to guide the team through the mapping process. The rules were: (1) The development of an extension to incorporate template specific needs should only be considered if absolutely necessary; (2) the DCS application profile was not to be modified, with only its documentation available to be improved; (3) mapping DMP Template questions to “description” fields in the DCS application profile should be avoided if possible; and (4) if extensions were to be considered, they should be limited to a single extension to cover all DMP templates. New fields should only cover funder specific concepts that could not be mapped to any individual field or set of fields in the DCS application profile. Additionally any new field should not have been originally covered by the DCS [user stories](#).

The starting point to the mapping process was a spreadsheet establishing mappings between the DCS application standard and the H2020 DMP template, provided by Simon Oblasser. In the spreadsheet, DMP Template questions were sorted into three categories, in accordance with their potential to be mapped into the DCS application profile. The categories were the

following: (1) Completely answerable, where existing fields were sufficient to answer the question completely; (2) partially answerable, where parts of the question can be answered using existing fields, however some information may not be included; and (3) cannot be answered, where there were no fields suitable to answer the given question. The common reasons for partial answerability or lack of answerability stemmed from the fact that fields for “the narrative” were missing, e.g., one can indicate that data will not be shared openly, but there was no field to provide explanation. The spreadsheet was used as a [template](#) for the analysis of the remainder DMP Templates.

Results

This section details the proposals that resulted from the process of mapping multiple DMP Templates to the DCS application profile.

Proposal for changes in the documentation of the DCS application profile

The descriptions of several fields were considered to be inadequate. As such the team [proposed description changes](#) to the following fields: Contributor, Metadata, DataQualityAssurance and SecurityAndPrivacy.

Proposal for the changes in the structure of the DCS application profile

The DCS application profile was also considered for a very limited revision. As such, the team proposed a change in the field [dataset/quality assurance](#), which is a String with a nested data structure, to change its cardinality from 0..1 to 0..n. “Should be focused on calibration, ensuring accuracy and reliability of data. Naming conventions fit better under metadata.”.

Proposal for a *funder-extension* to the DCS application profile

In accordance with the established rules, it was decided that instead of creating multiple funder extensions to address individual DMP templates. The effort would instead be directed into creating a single funder-extension that would aggregate all new fields necessary to any DMP template. A full listing of all the new fields that were considered, can be found in the official [working documentation of issue 14](#).

Future Work

The limited time frame of the hackathon implies that the work plan must always be extremely focused on a limited number of objectives. The following are tasks that have resulted from the work developed in the hackathon: (1) Create guidance documents and mappings for funder templates; (2) Public review of documents created in this hackathon; (3) Apply the hackathon methodology to other DMP templates. This is a task that is already in progress; and (4) Release the DCS application profile funder-extension.